

University of Warsaw
 Faculty of "Artes Liberales"
 Centre for Studies on the Classical Tradition (OBTA)
 and the Cluster The Past for the Present

OUR MYTHICAL HISTORY

Children's and Young Adults' Culture
 in Response to the Heritage
 of Ancient Greece and Rome

International Conference
 Faculty of "Artes Liberales"
 University of Warsaw

May 22–26, 2019

ERC Consolidator Grant (681202)
 Our Mythical Childhood...
 The Reception of Classical Antiquity
 in Children's and Young Adults' Culture
 in Response to Regional
 and Global Challenges

MAY 22, 2019 (WEDNESDAY)

Collegium Artes Liberales (CLAS), Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, White Villa, Dobra 72, conference room

- 9.30 Opening of the Conference
 Introduction: Katarzyna Marciniak, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Prof. Robert A. Sucharski, Dean of the Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Ms. Gabriele Hermani, Science Counsellor at the German Embassy in Warsaw
 ● Prof. Jerzy Axer, Director of the Collegium Artes Liberales (CLAS), Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Our Mythical Surprise
- Inaugural Lecture in Latin
 Prof. Wilfried Stroh, Institute of Classical Philology, University of Munich, *De fabulis scaenicis in Germania exhibitis*
- 11.00–12.30 Ancient History – Our Histories
 Moderator: Renzo Tosi, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna
 ● Lisa Maurice, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University, *Reading the Graeco-Roman World from Right to Left: The Portrayal of Greeks and Romans in Jewish Children's Fiction*
 ● Valentina Garali, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, *The Irresistible Charm of History: Laura Orvieto's Narrative on Historical Themes*
 ● Sonja Schreiner, Department of Classical Philology, Medieval and Neolatin Studies, University of Vienna, *Reduced to Stereotypes vs. Historical Realism: Ancient People in Children's Literature in the 1950s and in the Third Millennium*
- 13.00 Paulina Buzniak, Nastazja Ciupa, and Jan Rusiński. Vernissage of the exhibition *Per aspera ad astra* in Honour of Professor Anna M. Komornicka (1920–2018) by the students of Prof. Błażej Ostojka Lniski's Studio of Lithography and Studio of Book Design and Illustrations, Academy of Fine Arts in Warsaw, University of Warsaw Gallery
- 14.00 Lunch for Speakers
- 15.00–16.30 The Romans Rule!
 Moderator: Bettina Kümmerling-Melbauer, German Department, University of Tübingen
 ● Ayelet Peer, Department of Classical Studies, Bar-Ilan University, *He Came, He Saw, He Conquered Hollywood: Julius Caesar in Popular Culture*
 ● Markus Janka, Institute of Classical Philology, University of Munich, *Rejuvenating Heroes of Roman History in Robert Harris' Novels and HBO's "Rome"*
 ● Raimund Fichtel, Institute of Classical Philology, University of Munich, *The Birth of the Suetonian Nero from the Spirit of Mythology and Its Modern Variations*
- 16.30–17.00 Coffee Break
- 17.00–18.00 ERC Grant Seminar Students' Session
 Moderator: Karolina Anna Kulpa, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Marta Piszczolinska, *Sparta between Myths and History – "The Wolf of Sparta" by Antonis Antoniadis and the Modern Hero of Ancient History*
 ● Anastasia Khru, *Alexander the Great, as Seen by Soviet Novelists*
 ● Krzysztof Rybak, *Our Honeyed History: The Ancient World in "The Book of Bees" and "The Book of Trees" by Piotr Socha and Wojciech Grykoswski*
 ● Anna Mik, *"Dobby is Free!" The House Elf as Spartacus of the Wizarding World*
 ● Olga Banasikowska, *"Classic History Lesson" by Jack Kaczmarek*
 ● Haruka Miwa, *Three Historical Heroes from a Neutral Point of View*
 ● Agnieszka Maciejewska, *To the Rescue of Alexandria – Cleopatra and Romans in "Caesar, Who's He?" Alain Surget's Series "Children of the Nile"*
 ● Viktoriya Bartshevich, *Have the Triumvirates Been Behind Everything? Nero, Caligula, Commodus in "The Trials of Apollo" by Rick Riordan*
- 18.00–18.30 Coffee Break
- 18.30 Our Mythical Evening
 ● Sonya Nevin and Steve Simons, Department of Humanities, University of Roehampton / Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Our Mythical Animations*
 ● Awards Ceremony Celebrating the Winners in the Video Competition *Antiquity-Camera-Action!*
- 20.30 Dinner for Speakers

MAY 23, 2019 (THURSDAY)

- 9.30–11.00 De viris mulieribusque illustribus – Schools Session
 ● Barbara Strycharczyk's Class, "Strumienie" High School in Józefów, *Jan Zamoyski – vir incomparabilis*
 ● Barbara Bibik's Class, Nicolaus Copernicus University Academic Junior and Senior High School in Toruń, *An Old Remedy for New Ills, or about the Renewal of the Republic according to Jan Zamoyski's "De senatu Romano libri II"*

- Anna Wojciechowska's Class, Mikołaj Rej XI High School in Warsaw, *Stanisław Kostka Potocki: The Taste of Beautiful Things*
 ● Janusz Ryba's Class, Bartłomiej Nowodworski I High School in Cracow, *De libertate Rei Publicae meriti... Krystyna Skarbek and Zdzisław Lubomirski in the Service of a Sovereign Republic*
- 11.00–11.15 Coffee Break
- 11.15–11.45 Belarusian and Russian Bursary Recipients' Session supervised by Hanna Paulouskaya, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Anastasia Ashveva, The School of Advanced Studies in the Humanities of the Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, *A Polish Mirror: Ancient Mythology in the USSR from Tadeusz Zieliński to Kazimierz Kumaniecki*
 ● Anastasiya Davydova, Faculty of Philology, Belarusian State University, *Mikhail Gasparov, or How to Make Greece Entertaining*
 ● Angelina Geras, Faculty of Philology, Belarusian State University, *"Socrates in Love": How to Introduce Plato to the Youngest*
 ● Alexandra Pisanuk, Faculty of Philology, Belarusian State University, *Ancient History in Contemporary Street Art of Modern Greece*
- 11.45–12.00 Coffee Break
- 12.00–13.00 Sonya Nevin and Steve Simons, Department of Humanities, University of Roehampton / Panoply Vase Animation Project, *Create Your Own Ancient Vase Workshop*
- 13.00–13.30 Susan Deacy, Department of Humanities, University of Roehampton, *Draw Your Hercules' Choice Workshop*
- 14.00 Lunch for Speakers
- 15.00–16.30 Young and Old between Rebellion and Admiration
 Moderator: Daniel A. Nkemleke, Department of English, University of Youndé 1
 ● Katarzyna Jerzak, Institute of Modern Languages, Pomorska Academy in Słupsk, *Mark Twain's "Innocents Abroad" (1869): An Irreverent Look of the New World Upon the Old*
 ● Hanna Paulouskaya, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *The Lives of Remarkable Ancients for Use of Soviet Youth*
 ● Edoardo Pecchini, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Promoting Mental Health through Classics: Icarus' Flight*
- 16.30–17.00 Coffee Break
- 17.00–18.00 Playing with History
 Moderator: Sheila Murnaghan, Department of Classical Studies, University of Pennsylvania
 ● Rachel Bryant-Davies, Department of Classics and Ancient History, Durham University, *"A nobler entertainment": Graeco-Roman History in British Children's Toys and Games, c. 1750–1914*
 ● Karolina Anna Kulpa, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *"Caesar and Cleopatra unite Rome and Egypt": An Irreverent Look of the New World Upon the Old*
 ● Veronique Dassen, Department of Historical Sciences, ERC Advanced Grant Project *Locus Ludi*, University of Fribourg and Ulrich Schädler, Swiss Museum of Games, *Gods, Heroes, and Monuments: Greek and Roman Antiquity in Games*
- 19.30 Dinner for Speakers
- MAY 24, 2019 (FRIDAY)**
- 10.00–11.30 The True History?
 Moderator: Markus Janka, Institute of Classical Philology, University of Munich
 ● Bettina Kümmerling-Melbauer, German Department, University of Tübingen, *"The most splendid guy of ancient history": Facts and Fiction on Spartacus in Leftist German Children's Literature*
 ● Giacomo Savani, Department of Classics, University of Leeds, *Getting the Narrative Right: Authority and Imagination in the Educational Book "Life in the Roman World: Roman Leicester", Co-authored by Giacomo Savani, Sarah Scott and Mathew Morris*
 ● Sheila Murnaghan, Department of Classical Studies, University of Pennsylvania, *Champion of History, Invertebrate Liar: Biographies of Heinrich Schliemann for Young Readers*
- 11.30–12.00 Coffee Break
- 12.00–13.30 Once Upon a Time and Today in Greece
 Moderator: Elena Iakovou, Seminar for Classical Philology, University of Göttingen
 ● Deborah H. Roberts, Department of Classics, Haverford College, *The Gadfly and Athenian Girlhood: Socrates in Historical Fiction for Children*
 ● Robert A. Sucharski, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Witold Makowiecki and His Two Novels on the Mediterranean in the Sixth Century BC*
 ● Przemysław Kaniński and Przemysław Kordos, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Ancient History in Contemporary Modern Greek Comics*
- 14.00 Lunch for Speakers

- 15.00–17.00 Greece and Rome between the African and the Slavic Traditions
 Tele-bridge with Stefano Colangelo and the students from his International Lab on Foreignness, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna
 Moderator: Hanna Paulouskaya, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Krishni Burns, Department of Classics and Mediterranean Studies, University of Illinois Chicago, *Spectacular Colonialism: Naumachia in "Children of Blood and Bone"*
 ● Daniel A. Nkemleke, Divine Che Neba, and Eleanor A. Dasi, Department of English, University of Youndé 1, *Mythic Fulfillment and Performance in the Bafut Abimifor and the Greek Dionysian Festivals*
 ● Karoline Thaidigsmann, Slavic Department, University of Heidelberg, *Post-Socialist Identity between Slavic Gods, the Graeco-Roman Tradition and Western Christianity. A Reading of Dorota Terakowska's Crossover Novel "The Loneliness of the Gods"*
- 17.00 Dinner for Speakers
- 19.30 Concert in the Warsaw Philharmonic for Speakers
- MAY 25, 2019 (SATURDAY)**
- Collegium Artes Liberales (CLAS), Faculty of "Artes Liberales" UW, White Villa, Dobra 72, conference room
- 10.00–11.30 (Ancient) History Is Fun!
 Moderator: David Morin, Department of Classical Philology, University of Ljubljana
 ● Elizabeth Hale, School of Arts, University of New England, *Funny Bones: Archaeology, Humour, and Australian Children's Books*
 ● Owen Hodgkinson, Department of Classics, University of Leeds, *Groovy Greeks, Rotten and Ruthless Romans: The Classical Past in the "Horrible Histories" Series*
 ● Elżbieta Olechowska, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Ancient History in DC's "Legends of Tomorrow", Season 3, Episodes 1, 6, 18 ("Aruba-Con", "Helen Hunt", "The Good, the Bad, and the Cuddly")*
- 11.30–12.00 Coffee Break
- 12.00–13.30 History Engaged
 Moderator: Elżbieta Olechowska, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw
 ● Edith Hall, Department of Classics, King's College London, *Secular Ethics for Young Socialists: F.J. Gould on Ancient History, 1906–1913*
 ● Nick Lowe, Royal Holloway, University of London, *Children of History: Situating Youth Consciousness in Fictional Greek Antiquity*
 ● Frances Foster, Faculty of Education, University of Cambridge, *Another Late Antiquity: John Christopher's "Fireball" (via Skype)*
- 14.00 Lunch for Speakers
- 15.30–17.00 Between Myth and History
 Moderator: Deborah H. Roberts, Department of Classics, Haverford College
 ● Jerzy Axer, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *"By Oak, Ash, and Thorn": The Meaning of the Lessons in Roman History with Puck of Pook's Hill*
 ● Jan Kieniewicz, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *A Knight with No Blemish and without Fear: Heroic Myth in Polish Children Novel and National Identity during Captivity*
 ● Katarzyna Marciniak, Faculty of "Artes Liberales", University of Warsaw, *Once and Future Antiquity: Greek and Roman Heritage in the BBC's "Merlin"*
- 17.30 Summary of the Conference
- 19.00 Dinner for Speakers
- MAY 26, 2019 (SUNDAY)**
- 9.30 Cultural Programme for Speakers
 Trip to Żelazowa Wola – Frédéric Chopin's Birthplace
- 14.00 Lunch for Speakers
- 15.00 Individual Talks and Consultations / Warsaw Book Fair at the National Stadium
- 19.00 Dinner for Speakers
- For more see: www.omc.obta.al.uw.edu.pl
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